

‘Nietzsche has shown us how the philosophy of science should be done’: Reading MacIntyre, Nietzsche, Newman, and Marx

Alasdair MacIntyre — in memoriam

Babette Babich

‘Nietzsche’s Titanism’

Alasdair Chalmers MacIntyre (12 January 1929-21 May 2025) was born in Glasgow, Scotland, the son of two physicians, Eneas MacIntyre and Margaret Chalmers of Northern Irish, County Donegal, background, and MacIntyre remembered that his father was the first in his family who did not learn English “as a second language.” (MacIntyre and Nikulin, 1996, p. 671) MacIntyre grew up in London and took a degree in Classics from Queen Mary College, University of London in 1949. MacIntyre’s classical, philologist’s background is evident in the distinctions he makes in his discussion of virtue, especially the ‘heroic’ in *After Virtue* (MacIntyre, 1981, pp. 121ff.) and in his review of the translation of Nietzsche’s *Will to Power* which he titled ‘Nietzsche’s Titanism.’ (MacIntyre, 1969) The title refers to the tragic fate of the Titans by way of a letter Nietzsche wrote from Turin in January of 1889, just before his famous collapse, to the classical historian, Jacob Burckhardt in Basel:

Dear Herr Professor, when it comes to it I too would very much prefer a professorial chair in Basle to being God; but I did not dare to go as far in my private egoism as to refrain for its sake from the creation of the world. (Nietzsche, cited in MacIntyre, 1969, p. 79)

‘Nietzsche’s Titanism’ fits to the extent that the Titan, Prometheus, first created human beings from clay, as Aeschylus recounts and Nietzsche repeats, citing Goethe, in his tragedy book. Günther Anders uses the same reference for the same reasons in his 1956 book on the ‘outdatedness’ or antiquatedness of humanity, writing of “Promethean shame” (Anders, 2016), that is: the shame of human beings comparing themselves with the things they have made (see Babich, 2025a).

MacIntyre’s review of Kaufmann and Hollingdale’s translation (which translation, in the fashion characteristic of reviews, remains largely undiscussed) begins with the older charge of Nietzsche’s insanity (in Plato’s *Apology*, Socrates argues that one should begin by addressing standing objections) before considering the status of a work an author never published. Yet, when “a philosopher’s life is relevant to the understanding of his philosophy,”¹ as in Nietzsche’s case,

Special interest attaches to the work he did not publish, to first drafts, to notes and jottings. So it is with Pascal and so pre-eminently with Nietzsche. Between 1883 and 1888 Nietzsche kept notebooks on theories which he hoped to embody finally in a book called *The Will to Power*, perhaps sub-titled *Attempt at a Revaluation of All Values*. *The Antichrist*, written in 1888, was for a time thought of as the first of

¹ This is Nietzsche’s argument on the importance of the ‘person’ where we have little textual evidence, making Diogenes Laërtius’ *Lives* indispensable. (Nietzsche, 1980, 1, pp. 802-803).

four books of a work to have the latter title. But in 1888 he abandoned the project of *The Will to Power*. (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 79)

Relevant in this context, MacIntyre would befriend Tracy Burr Strong [1943-2022] who had written a Harvard dissertation on Nietzsche in 1968 and whom he met when Strong, as a junior political philosopher, was asked to offer a commentary at a conference at which MacIntyre spoke.¹

In the rest of his review, MacIntyre discusses Nietzsche philosophically and logically:

THE FOUNDATION OF Nietzsche's doctrine was a profound philosophical conception, derived partly from Kant and Hume, partly from Protagoras and Heraclitus.

Logic is bound to the condition: assume there are identical cases. In fact, to make possible logical thinking and inferences, this condition must first be treated fictitiously as fulfilled. That is: the will to logical truth can be carried through only after a fundamental *falsification* of all events is assumed... (512).

That is, we can only reason on the assumption that the same object or event can be clarified and classified by means of the same descriptive expression; but in fact, so Nietzsche tells us, following Heraclitus, everything changes and nothing remains the same, there are no like cases, and therefore the assumption on which all reasoning rests is false. (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 80)²

The issue for Nietzsche would be axiomatic (see on Kant, axiomatic systems, and Nietzsche, the axiomatician and cosmologist, Rudolf Kurth, 1956) but post Karl Popper, the notion of falsification would be as relevant for MacIntyre as logic. Popper was concerned, as MacIntyre was well aware, with the foundation of logic in Parmenides (Popper, 1998)³ and the challenge of Heraclitus. The problem as MacIntyre objects is the general problem with skepticism (and MacIntyre was the editor of an edition of Hume's essays [1965]) but significantly MacIntyre links Nietzsche with Kant (this is less commonly done than it should be) together with the notion of the 'sovereign individual,'⁴ articulated for Kant, MacIntyre argues, in terms of

a moral law which every rational being utters to himself. This law is unconditionally binding upon all rational beings and what it enjoins us to is the doing of our duty for no other motive than that it is our duty; we must not obey the precepts of the moral law out of interest or in the pursuit of happiness. Furthermore, our knowledge of the moral law is prior to and independent of our knowledge of

¹ See for a recollection (and illustration) — including a reference to MacIntyre, 1991 — Strong, 2023, p. 93

² „Die Logik ist geknüpft an die Bedingung: gesetzt, es giebt identische Fälle. Thatsächlich, damit ogisch gedacht und geschlossen werde, muß diese Bedingung erst als erfüllt fingirt werden. Das heißt: der Wille zur logischen Wahrheit kann erst sich vollziehen, nachdem eine grundsätzliche Fälschung alles Geschehens vorgenommen ist. Woraus sich ergibt, daß hier ein Trieb waltet, der beider Mittel fähig ist, zuerst der Fälschung und dann der Durchführung Eines Gesichtspunktes: die Logik stammt nicht aus dem Willen zur Wahrheit.“ (Nietzsche, 1980, 11, pp. 633-634)

³ See on Popper and Paul Feyerabend's own interest in the Presocratic philosophers, Babich, 2024, pp. 131-132.

⁴ See Owen, 1999 and for an analytic discussion of the 'puzzle of Nietzsche's virtues,' Dennis, 2018 and see, for another account, the section "Promises, Law, and Debt: Nobility and the Sovereign" in Babich, 2017, pp. 178-182.

the divine will; we are in fact able to judge that what God commands is right only because we have an independent moral view of what Rightness is. (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 80)

Thus, at “the centre of this autonomous morality,” MacIntyre argues, contra Kant,

there lies the notion of a body of precepts which have the force and authority of law, but which no one utters to us except ourselves. But how can I be the author of the moral law? How can any body of precepts which I utter to myself be unconditionally binding upon me? (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 81)

In his critique of Kant, MacIntyre realizes that more than the prosaic sky hook usually required in analytic philosophy will be needed, arguing that:

If the individual is made sovereign in the realm of values, if everyone has the right to declare what principles have authority over him, then what authority do any principles have over anyone? (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 81)

To this extent, where Kant fails — MacIntyre maintains that critiques “such as the Kantian do in fact fail” — Nietzsche begins. Strong took this critique and undertook to resolve its tensions as point of departure in his *Nietzsche and the Politics of Transfiguration* (Strong 1996), whereby for MacIntyre, “the transvaluation of values is one only to be undertaken by someone whose sense of his own mission is at least on the scale of those who taught that they were sent by God or spoke with His voice.” (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 82) Logically indeed, for MacIntyre,

Nietzsche was all too uneasily aware of the scale of his own claims and that this belonged to the nature of his task and had nothing to do with questions of personal vanity. When it came to it, he would very much have preferred a professorial chair in Basel to a task that carried with it the danger of self-deification. (MacIntyre, 1969, p. 82)

MacIntyre, the having of a PhD, and Nietzsche, who also did not have one, on ‘Science’

MacIntyre also had two graduate degrees in philosophy — an MA from Manchester, 1951, where he taught as lecturer (1951-1957) and Oxford in 1961. MacIntyre never took a PhD, a degree, it has been said, that at the time was regarded in England as an ‘American degree’ (obviously this is no longer the case). But throughout his life teaching in America, MacIntyre (famously/infamously) regarded those with doctoral degrees with suspicion. Thus the present author is mindful that she was addressed (for the very first time) as ‘doctor’ by Professor MacIntyre, interviewing for a post at a university where he was teaching. The interview was catastrophic but we became friends, Aristotle style, for life.

We met on occasion and we corresponded at first via post and later by email. I sent him my essay on the Sokal hoax in 1996 and MacIntyre replied in a letter thanking me and calling it ‘by far’ the best thing he had read on the topic (the essay was otherwise unreceived, anathema, although it inspired the editor of the journal, *Common Knowledge* Jeffrey Perl, as he also told me in a letter, to organize a section around it). (See Babich, 1997)

One does not question science in the age of science, then or now.

Not unless you are MacIntyre, with humor and a vastly broader perspective, bringing in the townspeople, with pitchforks, pitching. Thus in “A Disquieting Suggestion,” at the start of *After Virtue*, MacIntyre used the example of cliché anti-science sentiment, born of ignorance and blaming and then proceeding in MacIntyre’s thought experiment (MacIntyre was classically analytic) to destroy science which destruction would perforce and classically necessitate the subsequent reconstitution of science from fragmentary remainders (and superstitious conviction) (MacIntyre, 1981, pp. 1-5) It’s a perfect analogy and authors have noted parallels with Feyerabend, Lakatos¹ Kuhn, and others.²

To be sure, MacIntyre’s interest in science was far from desultory. Thus a few years after the Sokal hoax took hold, he wrote a preface for the second of a two-volume collection I edited on *Nietzsche and the Sciences*, asking (and answering) with his characteristic precision:

Why should a philosopher of the natural sciences be interested in Nietzsche’s writings? How one answers this question will depend in part on who you are. Those who identify themselves wholeheartedly with Nietzsche’s central positions — and this is a harder task than is commonly supposed — have a straightforward answer. Nietzsche has shown us how the philosophy of science should be done. And we have an excellent model for such a response in *Nietzsche’s Philosophy of Science* by the editor of these volumes. (MacIntyre, 1999, xv)

Similarly in the review I began by citing, MacIntyre had instanced Nietzsche’s critique of logic in connection with a critique of Kant and his argument.

I have taught MacIntyre’s work throughout my philosophical teaching career. My reasons for this had to do with MacIntyre’s capacity to draw complex connections: one cannot begin to understand Max Weber’s *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism* (Weber, 2002), and that is the history of contemporary world with all its social issues and injustice, without his chapter on “Machiavelli, Luther, Hobbes [complete with a parenthesis on tax loopholes],³ and Spinoza.” (MacIntyre, 1996, pp. 121-145) As MacIntyre observes:

Machiavelli and Luther mark in their different ways the break with the clerical, synthesizing society of the Middle Ages, and the distinctive moves into the modern world. In both writers there appears a figure who is absent from moral theories in periods when Plato and Aristotle dominate it, the figure of “the individual.” (MacIntyre, 1996, pp. 121)

If MacIntyre brilliantly analysed Hobbes — it helps to be, as Hobbes was, as MacIntyre was, a classicist — it was his understanding of science that would be useful for me as I continued to write and reflect on the stakes of the so-called ‘science wars’ connected as these were with the fortunes

¹ MacIntyre himself references Lakatos (1974), see for one discussion, Miner (2001).

² See for a general discussion focused on ethics, Caiazza (2014).

³ “(It is always a sobering thought that the income tax accountant searching for legal loopholes for his business clients is the spiritual descendant of Pym and Hampden.)” MacIntyre, 1996, p. 131.

of philosophy as such, its potential and its ultimate limitation as we know it today (analytic as it is now and cannot but remain). Elsewhere, I reflect on the political fortunes of a philosophical career of brilliance, frustration, and (notably successful) re-invention in the complicated case of Bruno Latour (1947-2022, see Babich, 2017b). But MacIntyre exemplifies the courage to advert to the influence of the political in what counts (and can be counted) as a ‘fact’ in “The Idea of Social Science.”¹

Using the language of traditional philosophy of science, MacIntyre reminds us that “[i]nstrumentalism, like attempts to refute skepticism, is characteristically a sign of a tradition in crisis.” (MacIntyre, 1977, 459) There influenced by Feyerabend’s critique in *Against Method* (1974), MacIntyre offers a received reading of Galileo (the discussion is preceded by an analysis of Hamlet — and Nietzsche also references Hamlet with respect to epistemological crisis — as MacIntyre points out that certain aspects must remain “ineffable”).² Arguably, MacIntyre offers what remain (to date) untapped possibilities for philosophy of science, natural and social,³ making an historically informed, and traditional, case for “the continuous reconstruction of the scientific tradition” (MacIntyre, 1977, pp. 463) just to the extent that we err (this again would be why we need to read Nietzsche and Feyerabend — and Mach) in our understanding of various scientists.

MacIntyre analyses crises that have in the interim only been updated, emphasizing that the epistemological depends upon “a number of conceptual connections.” (MacIntyre, 1977, pp. 463) Naming Feyerabend “the Emerson of the philosophy of science” (MacIntyre, 1977, pp. 465)⁴ — a coordination that permits MacIntyre to articulate incommensurability in *After Virtue*, MacIntyre emphasizes that Feyerabend must be read in concert with Michael Polanyi — the physicist and philosopher, Patrick Aidan Heelan (1926-2015) would argue the same — (noting that Kuhn’s writings are seemingly in debt to Polanyi’s unadverted, and there is a long list of unadverted, influence in Kuhn). Thereby Feyerabend, who was like Heelan, a physicist, can be recognized as holding with an ideal of a unitary tradition, such that in consequence, MacIntyre can argue that

he rejects it and has turned himself into the Emerson of the philosophy of science; not “Every man his own Jesus,” but “Every man his own Galileo.”) He does not see the omnipresence of conflict — sometimes latent — within living traditions. (MacIntyre, 1977, pp. 465; cf. on Heelan, Feyerabend, and Galileo, Babich, 2023).⁵

At issue is epistemological crisis, “conceptual incommensurability,” scheme to scheme, without bridges or transitions and MacIntyre’s “A Disquieting Suggestion” (MacIntyre, 1981, pp. 1f) works as an almost cinematic illustration of *rational* chassis, arguably lending philosophy its best sci-fi fairy tale since Lucian’s Ἀληθῆ διηγήματα (*Vera Historia*). (Lucian, 1913) Anticipating Ian Hacking’s ‘confession’ in his 2001 inaugural lecture at the College de France (Hacking, 2002), MacIntyre reminds us that “The theory of scientific rationality has to be embedded in a philosophy

¹ See MacIntyre, 1981, pp. 88-108 and see too “‘Fact,’ Explanation, and Expertise” MacIntyre, 1981, pp. 79-87.

² See Feyerabend (1974) for a nuanced historiographical and material-cum-experimentalist reflection on Galileo.

³ There are some discussions if they but tend to sidestep the question of “how the philosophy of science should be done,” see Turner (2003).

⁴ And MacIntyre will conclude (he had earlier referred with some humor to a possible world featuring “Kafka’s Theory of Knowledge”), citing Lakatos’ charge that Kuhn is the “Kafka of the history of science” (1977, pp. 472).

⁵ MacIntyre’s account obscures the light of Feyerabend’s own insights. See, on Feyerabend, Babich, 2024 and 2025b along with hermeneutic philosophy of science, and cf., on Heelan and Duhem etc., Babich, 2023.

of history.” (MacIntyre, 1977, pp. 460) This ‘embedding’ allows us to reflect on nothing less historically recalcitrant than ‘incommensurable schemes.’ Thus MacIntyre can read Lakatos (where others might read Laudan), with the difference being a matter of the distinction between rational assessments of methodologies and pure pragmatism, utilitarianism being the automatic sell that it is in Anglophone, particularly US, philosophy.

P.M.S. Hacker likewise invokes the distinction between the social sciences and philosophy and goes on to correct Donald Davidson’s hermeneutic deficiencies as an error in argumentation inasmuch as

one can surely identify a language-using community independently of finding it possible to translate their language, for example, by reference to their way of life or the artefacts they produce. Etruscan has still not been translated, and may be impossible to translate without another Rosetta Stone, but there is no doubt that Etruscans spoke a language and that the surviving inscriptions are indeed such. It may be impossible to translate a language given the non-cooperation of the speakers (if they are an unfriendly lot), or perhaps they speak a tonal language of such refinement of tonal differentiation we cannot distinguish different words as they can. (Hacker, 1996, p. 291; cf. Davidson, 1973-1974)

MacIntyre speaks of incommensurability and language and narrative and Heidegger had made a related point about language (and tone) in 1927. And Heelan (1971) uses language to speak of the logic of framework transpositions with respect to quantum mechanics and objectivity.

In this way, Nietzsche originally claimed he was the very first to raise “the question of science” (as problematic, as a question) just as MacIntyre observed that a Nietzschean philosophy of science “should” raise the question of science. Elsewhere, I have argued that traditionally philosophy is ancilla to theology but, by contrast with modern science, theology rarely resists philosophy as philosophy is needed and used by the theologians.

Does science, natural and social science, ‘need’ philosophy, does it require philosophy of science? Scientists do not seem to think/say so (see for further references, Babich, 2021) and Stephen Hawking once declared ‘philosophy is dead’ (See Warman, 2011 and Egnor, 2015). Dismayed at this and other such pronouncements, analytic philosophers argue that scientists be ‘required’ to take courses in (analytic) philosophy.¹ The response from STEM has been to eliminate required courses in the humanities overall, effected at an administrative level,² leading to cuts in course offerings, in programs, and eliminating entire departments.

MacIntyre has other recommendations for the university.

Newman and Marx

In a contemporary context, MacIntyre addresses John Henry Cardinal Newman’s the ‘idea of a university’ (MacIntyre, 2009). Newman, who like Nietzsche and MacIntyre also studied Classics,

¹ See for references and discussion, Metcalf, 2022 and Frank, 2004.

² See for one recent example, Morris, 2025.

is nearly cliché and MacIntyre does not hesitate to remind the reader of attacks, likewise cliché. It is not held, MacIntyre observes, that Newman is ‘wrong’ but that he is irrelevant (MacIntyre, 2009, pp. 347), an argument not unlike those who critique AI in education (can’t be stopped, happening anyway, will be a ‘good thing’).¹ Thus, for MacIntyre:

To criticise contemporary universities from Newman’s standpoint would be, on their view, like blaming a jet engine for not having the excellences of a windmill. (MacIntyre, 2009, pp. 347)

But, as opposed to philosophy, it is theology, ‘queen of the sciences,’ that is key:

Without a recognition of theology as the key discipline, the university curriculum, so Newman argued, will disintegrate into a fragmented multiplicity of disciplines, each self-defining, each claiming autonomy in its own sphere. (MacIntyre, 2009, pp. 349)

MacIntyre distinguishes the nature of proofs for the existence of God and the relation of the same to the nature of God, but claims regarding the economy seem most crucial as MacIntyre summarizes arguments that are yet more salient in the interval, given the generic success of STEM:

Universities today would not survive, let alone flourish, if they were not able credibly to promise to their students a gateway to superior career possibilities and to donors and governments both a supply of appropriately skilled manpower and research that contributes to economic growth. Universities, that is to say, promise to be cost-effective enterprises. (MacIntyre, 2009, pp. 350)

Thus MacIntyre articulates the presuppositions of the practical syllogism as a guide to decision making, what Heelan, the Dublin born Jesuit and one of MacIntyre’s Irish friends, would call “rules for the discernment of spirits.”

Writing an introduction for Antonio de Nicolas’ translation of the Ignatian *Spiritual Exercises*, Heelan explains a phenomenology of internal consciousness as a hermeneutic of religious or spiritual affect:

a manner of experiencing and then discerning, that is, evaluating, the spiritual affects of (what Ignatius called) “consolation” and “desolation,” first in the course of such imaginative exercises, then in contemplating the world around that God made, and finally at the heart of daily human living. (Heelan, 1986, p. x)

Appealing to the disciplines, MacIntyre writes that

Sometimes we need to correct what economists tell us by appealing to the historians, and sometimes of course vice versa. Sometimes we need to correct what neurophysiologists tell us by appealing to psychologists, and sometimes vice versa,

¹ See, per contra, Babich, 2025c. Online — there to be ‘scraped,’ and hence the claim of inevitability.

and sometimes we may need as well or instead to go to novelists or dramatists. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 353)

The argument is classical, found in both Plato and Aristotle. Thus for MacIntyre:

We all of us therefore need to be schooled in a number of disciplines, just because each has its own methods, insights and standards. To be educated is, on this view, not only to know how to bring each discipline to bear in appropriate ways, but also how to respond to the unjustified claims made in the name of each. And for this we need not the contracted mind of the specialist, but a different sort of mind. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 353)

Quoting Newman on the perfection of the mind to this same end,

true enlargement of mind which is the power of viewing many things [at once] as one whole, of referring them severally to their [true] place in the universal system, of understanding their respective values, and determining their mutual dependence. (Citing Newman, 1881, pp. 136-137 in MacIntyre, 2009, p. 353)

The universities need to be reformed in the direction of being (just as philosophy of science “should be”) what they ‘should be’ as universities in terms of the education offered to students and not less in terms of the formation presupposed for the educators themselves. Not currently standard, as MacIntyre suggests:

We should notice too that the teaching of this kind of curriculum will require a corresponding kind of education for teachers, since we shall need teachers of literature who are well informed about biochemistry and teachers of physics who are able to think historically, all of them being at home with the relevant mathematics. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 354)

MacIntyre goes on to ask the question of human nature, often featured in the title of introductory philosophy courses (as, for example, ‘Philosophy of Human Nature’):

We are, according to physics, composed of particles interacting with each other and with our environment. Chemistry tells us that we are sites of a variety of reactions; biology, as Newman was shortly to learn from Darwin, that we are in key part what we are because of the evolution of species. Sociology and economics characterise the structure of our roles and relationships; history informs us that we are what our past has made us and what we have made of our past. And theology views all these same features from a very different perspective. The crucial questions are: “In what then does the unity of a human being consist? And what is it about human beings that enables them to ask this question about themselves? (MacIntyre, 2009, pp. 354-355)

As opposed to arguing for philosophy as “a general education requirement” (to cite the title of Metcalf, 2022), theology is not one discipline or science among others for MacIntyre on his account of the (ideal) university:

Take away theology and the curriculum will be fragmented into a series of specialised disciplines, leaving at best the possibility of some kind of factitious unity imposed by social agreement. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 357)

If ‘discernment’ was Heelan’s term, MacIntyre’s term was *phronesis*, the prudential. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 359) Here MacIntyre offers a series of variations on possible responses to the practical question “What are you doing?” — questions which may be answered in one way or another by way of an application of the practical syllogism.

MacIntyre has a range of books addressing this question and its responses, including treatments of question-variants, from the banal to the personal, reflective and psychoanalytic but the instability of the ‘factitious unity imposed by social agreement’ is his greatest concern, and towards the end of his essay, MacIntyre alludes to George Orwell who mused, “As I write, highly civilized human beings are flying overhead, trying to kill me.” (Orwell, 1982, 35)

Key here is not reference to a hypothetical murderer (the Nazi that knocks on one’s door seeking a Jew who has taken refuge in one’s lodging, or the ‘trolley problem,’ murderous in one way or the other, at one’s hypothetical option), but the anonymous, the global reference, such that:

a surprising number of the major disorders of the latter part of the twentieth century and of the first decade of the twenty-first century have been brought about by some of the most distinguished graduates of some of the most distinguished universities in the world and this as the result of an inadequate general education, at both graduate and especially undergraduate levels, that has made it possible for those graduates to act decisively and deliberately without knowing what they were doing. (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 361)

As humans we do not typically know *what we are doing* when we act. This Aristotle argues: the right thing can be done by accident or rote and cannot be judged ‘right’ unless done for the right reason, by one who knows how and why. But we are often oblivious, as Nietzsche claims, “we are unknown to ourselves, we knowers!” (Nietzsche, 1980, 5, p. 247) Nietzsche’s ‘unknown to ourselves’ is not what MacIntyre means. For MacIntyre, at stake is a failure, in Aristotle’s perspective, of learning: a lack of education.

MacIntyre’s turn in closing remains practical and economic — citing the fiscal crisis of 1997 and naming yet another classicist by formation, “Newman’s Aristotelian contemporary, Karl Marx” (MacIntyre, 2009, p. 352, cf. Blackledge and Davidson, 2008, pp. xiii-1.)

‘With eager thought ... And now the sun had stretch’d out all the hills,’ — John Milton

This is a necrologue written by a friend, for a friend. Thus I quote Milton’s *Lycidas*, and echo Richard Kearney, who wrote of Bill Richardson (also a Jesuit, like the Irish Heelan, but Brooklyn born and whose family hailed, like MacIntyre’s, from the north of Ireland): “His likes will never be seen again’ *Ní beidh a leithéid ann arís*’.”¹

¹ See Richard Kearney, also for an illustration of confessional tensions (Kearney, 2017, p. 13).

We are less without Alasdair MacIntyre. And given that we still need to change the world, we need to read the classicists, MacIntyre, Nietzsche, Newman, and Marx.

Acknowledgments

The author is grateful to Guillemette Johnston and Allan Johnston. Some portions of the above section of this essay have been updated from the final section of Babich (2022).

References

- Anders, G. (2016). Promethean Shame. In: C. J. Muller, *Prometheanism, Prometheanism: Technology, Digital Culture, and Human Obsolescence*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, pp. 29-95. [1956]
- Babich, B. (2025a). Günther Anders's 'Promethean Shame': Technological *Ressentiment* and Surveillance. *Harvard Review of Philosophy*, Vol. XXXI, pp. 75-97. [2024]
- . (2025b). Feyerabend's 'Science as Art' and Aloïs Riegl: On Progress in Science and Art. *Borderless Philosophy*, 8, pp. 1-31. Online: https://www.academia.edu/129741148/Feyerabends_Science_as_Art_and_Alo%C3%AFs_Riegl_On_Progress_in_Science_and_Art.
- . (2025c). Nietzsche, AI and Poetic Artistry: Nietzsche's 'Hinzugedichtetes.' In: H. Bajohr, ed., *Thinking with AI. Machine Learning the Humanities*. London: Open Humanities, pp. 147-181. Online: https://www.academia.edu/128603966/Nietzsche_AI_and_Poetic_Artistry_On_Nietzsche_s_Hinzugedichtetes.
- . (2024). Reading Feyerabend Between Philosophy of Science, Hermeneutics — and God. *Epistemology & Philosophy of Science*, 61 (3) pp. 120-140.
- . (2023). Material Hermeneutics and Heelan's Philosophy of Technoscience. *AI & Society*, 38 (6), pp. 2177-2188.
- . (2022). From Nietzsche's & 'Educational Institutions' to Jaspers and MacIntyre and Newman on 'The Idea of the University'. *Existenz*, 15 (2), pp. 17-31.
- . (2021). On the Very Idea of a Philosophy of Science: On Chemistry and Cosmology in Nietzsche and Kant. *Axiomathes. Special Issue Epistemologia*, 31 (6), pp. 703-726.
- . (2017a) Nietzsche's Critique: Reading Kant's Critical Philosophy. In: M. Conard, ed., *Nietzsche and the Philosophers*. London: Routledge, pp. 169-192.

—. (2017b). Hermeneutics and Its Discontents in Philosophy of Science: On Bruno Latour, the “Science Wars,” Mockery, and Immortal Models. In: B. Babich, ed., *Hermeneutic Philosophies of Social Science*. Berlin: de Gruyter, pp. 163-187.

—. (1997). The Hermeneutics of a Hoax. *Common Knowledge*, 6 (2), pp. 23-33.

Blackledge, P. and N. Davidson. (2008). The Unknown Alasdair MacIntyre. In: P. Blackledge and N. Davidson, eds. *Alasdair MacIntyre’s Engagement with Marxism: Selected Writings 1953-1974*. Amsterdam: Brill, pp. xiii-l.

Caiazza, J. C. (2014). Paradigms, Traditions, and History: The Influence of Philosophy of Science on MacIntyre’s Ethical Thought. *American Catholic Philosophical Quarterly*, 88 (4), pp. 685-704.

Davidson, D. (1973-1974). On the Very Idea of a Conceptual Scheme. *Proceedings and Addresses of the American Philosophical Association*, 47, pp. 5-20.

Dennis, M. (2018). Nietzschean self-cultivation: Connecting his Virtues to His Ethical Ideal,” *Journal of Value Inquiry*, pp. 1-19.

Egnor, M. (2015). Stephen Hawking: ‘Philosophy Is Dead.’ *Science & Culture Today*. Online: https://scienceandculture.com/2015/08/stephen_hawking_3/.

Feyerabend, P. (1974). *Against Method*. London: Verso.

Frank, P. (2004). The Place of the Philosophy of Science in the Curriculum of the Physics Student. *Science and Education*, 13 (February), pp. 99-120.

Hacker, P.M.S. (1996). On Davidson’s Idea of a Conceptual Scheme. *Philosophical Quarterly*, 46 (184), pp. 289-307.

Hacking, I. (2002). Inaugural lecture: Chair of Philosophy and History of Scientific Concepts at the College de France, 16 January 2001. *Economy and Society*, 31 (1), pp. 1-14.

Heelan, P. A. (1986). Foreword. In: A. T. de Nicolas, trans. and ed. Ignatius de Loyola, *Powers of Imagining: A Philosophical Hermeneutic of Imagining Through the Collected Works of Ignatius de Loyola, with a Translation of These Works*. Albany, NY: SUNY Press, pp. ix-xiv.

—. P. A. (1971). The Logic of Framework Transpositions. *International Philosophical Quarterly*, 11 (3), pp. 314-334.

Heidegger, M. (1927) *Sein und Zeit*. Tübingen: Niemeyer.

Kearney, R. (2017). Bill was a beautiful man. In: B. Babich, ed., *William J. Richardson, S.J.: Reflections in memoriam*. New York: NNS Press, pp. 8-13.

Kurth, R. (1956). Kants 'Allgemeine Naturgeschichte und Theorie des Himmels' von 1755 und die moderne Wissenschaft. *Mitteilungen der Naturforschenden Gesellschaft in Bern, Neue Reihe*, 13, pp. 58-80.

Lakatos, I. (1974). History of Science and Its Rational Reconstructions. In: R. C. Buch and R. S. Cohen, eds., *Boston Studies in the Philosophy of Science, Vol 8*. Dordrecht: Reidel, pp. 91-136.

Lucian. (1913). A true story. In: A. M. Harmon, trans., *Lucian, Volume One*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, pp. 247-358.

MacIntyre, A., ed. (1965). *Hume's Ethical Writings: Selections from David Hume*. Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press.

—. (1969). Philosophy & Sanity. Nietzsche's Titanism. *Encounter*, 32 (4) (Apr.), pp. 79-82.

—. (1977). Epistemological Crises, Dramatic Narrative and the Philosophy of Science, *The Monist*, 60 (4) *Historicism and Epistemology*, pp. 453-472.

—. (1981). *After Virtue*. Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press.

—. "The Idea of Political Theory: Reflections on the Self in Political Time and Place by Tracy B. Strong," *Ethics*, 101 (4), pp. 878-879.

—. (1996). *A Short History of Ethics*. New York: Simon and Schuster. [1966]

—. (1999). Preface. In: B. Babich, ed., *Nietzsche, Epistemology, and Philosophy of Science: Nietzsche and the Sciences II*. Dordrecht: Kluwer, pp. xv-xvii.

—. (2009). The Very Idea of a University: Aristotle, Newman, and Us. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 57 (4), pp. 347-362.

—. and D. Nikulin. (1996). Interview. *Wahre Selbsterkenntnis durch Verstehen unserer selbst aus der Perspektive anderer. Deutsche Zeitschrift für Philosophie*, 44 (4), pp. 671-684.

Metcalf, T. (2022). The Case for Philosophy as a General-Education Requirement. *Teaching Philosophy*, 45 (3), pp. 299-326.

Miner, R. (2001). Lakatos and MacIntyre on Incommensurability and the Rationality of Theory-Change. *Epistemologia XXIV*, pp. 221-236.

Morris, E. D. (2025). Unyoke the Sciences From the Humanities. *Science and Culture* (August 7). Online: <https://thedispatch.com/article/sciences-humanities-trump-faculty/>.

Newman, J. H. (1881). Discourse VI: Knowledge Viewed in Relation to Learning. In: *The Idea of A University Defined and Illustrated: In Nine Discourses Delivered to the Catholics of Dublin*. London, UK: Pickering and Co. pp. 124-150.

Nietzsche, F. (1980). *Kritische Studienausgabe*. G. Colli and M. Montinari, eds., Berlin: de Gruyter.

Orwell, G. (1982). *The Lion and the Unicorn: Socialism and the English Genius*. London: Penguin.

Owen, D. (1999). Nietzsche, Enlightenment and the Problem of Noble Ethics in: J. Lippitt, ed., *Nietzsche's Futures*. Basingstoke: Macmillan, pp. 3-29.

Popper, K. (1998). *The World of Parmenides: Essays on the Presocratic Enlightenment*, edited by A. F. Petersen, with the assistance of J. Mejer. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.

Strong, B. B. (2023) Tracy Burr Strong on Cavell on Presence and Nietzsche on Love. In: B. Strong, ed., *Tracy Burr Strong (6 August 1943 - 11 May 2022): Academic reflections in memoriam*. New York: NNS Press, pp. 81-110.

Strong, T. B. (1996) *Nietzsche and the Politics of Transfiguration*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Turner, S. (2003). MacIntyre and the Philosophy of the Social Sciences. In: M. C. Murphy, ed., *Alasdair MacIntyre*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 70-93.

Warman, M. (2011). Stephen Hawking Tells Google "Philosophy Is Dead." *Telegraph*, May 17.

Weber, M. (2002). *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism*, trans. Pe R. Baehr and G. C. Wells. London: Penguin [1904/1905].